

Zincate-Mediated Arylation Reactions of Acridine: Pre- and Postarylation Structural Insights

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This study explores the synthetic utility of homo(aryl) lithium zincate reagents $[\text{LiZnPh}_3]$ (2) and $[\text{Li}_2\text{ZnPh}_4]$ (3), made by cocomplexation of variable amounts of their monometallic components LiPh and ZnPh_2 (1), as chemoselective nucleophilic arylating reagents. Lithium zincates 2 and 3 were both characterized by multinuclear (^1H , ^{13}C , and ^7Li) NMR spectroscopy, and in the case of 2, a classical reagent in heterobimetallic chemistry, the molecular structure of its *On*Bu₂ solvate $[\text{LiZnPh}_3(\text{OnBu}_2)_2] \cdot 2 \cdot 2\text{OBu}_2$ has been established by X-ray crystallography. Using the synthetically relevant N-heterocyclic molecule acridine (*acr*, NC_{13}H_9), a new zincate-mediated arylating approach is demonstrated which allows the chemoselective arylation of *acr* at its C9 position, affording 9,10-dihydro-9-phenylacridine (4) in 95% yield using microwave irradiation (125 °C, 20 min). These conditions are in contrast with previous transition-metal-catalyzed methodologies using ZnPh_2 as an arylating reagent, which require significantly longer reaction times (130 °C, 20 h). Oxidation of 4 with DDQ furnished 9-phenylacridine (5) in a 71% yield. New insights into the constitution of the intermediate organometallic species involved in these reactions prior to the hydrolysis step have been gained by trapping homometallic $[(\text{THF})_3\text{Li}(\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{-Ph})]$ (6). Interestingly the reaction of *acr* with 3 equiv of PhLi/TMEDA led to the isolation of a different product, namely the novel paramagnetic $[(\text{THF})(\text{TMEDA})\text{Li}\{\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{-Ph}\}^{\cdot-}]$ (7), which contains a radical anion of 9-phenylacridine. The structure of the donor-acceptor complex $[(\text{acr})\text{ZnPh}_2]$ (8) has also been included as a result of the reaction of 1 with *acr*.

INTRODUCTION

Nitrogen-containing heteroaromatic ring systems are found widely in natural products, biologically active molecules, and pharmaceuticals.¹ Acridine (*acr*) scaffolds in particular (Figure 1) exhibit important biological activities, including anticancer,²

Figure 1. IUPAC numbering system of acridine (*acr*).

antibacterial,^{1a} and antifungal actions.³ Notably, their capacity to function as an intercalating ligand with DNA and related systems has earned them a prominent place in the field of chemical biology.⁴ Surprisingly, despite their synthetic relevance, the methods available for the efficient functionalization of nonsubstituted acridine motifs are limited.⁵ Thus, most

of the approaches described in the literature rely heavily on the assembly of prefunctionalized ring systems.^{1a,h,6}

Recent studies by Chatani and Tobisu have shown that regioselective C–H arylation of a range of electron-deficient N-heterocyclic molecules, including acridine, can be readily accomplished by neutral arylzinc reagents, but only under transition-metal catalysis.^{1g,5c,7} This method builds on the well-established reactivities of polar organolithium and Grignard reagents, which undergo 1,2-addition to pyridines, affording dihydropyridines which can subsequently be rearomatized via oxidation to yield 2-substituted products.⁸ By using either nickel^{1g,7} or rhodium^{5c} catalysts, it is possible to activate milder organozinc reagents such as ZnPh_2 (1), which offer greater regioselectivities and functional group tolerance, toward the nucleophilic arylation of the electron-deficient N-heterocyclic substrate.^{1g} Mechanistic studies suggest that in this approach

ZnPh₂ plays an important role, by activating the aromatic substrate and transferring its aryl substituent to the transition-metal catalyst¹⁵ as well as acting as an internal oxidant. Notwithstanding, it should be noted that these reactions still require the use of harsh reaction conditions, involving long reaction times (up to 20 h) and high temperatures (60–130 °C).^{1g,7}

In contrast with this approach, we have recently disclosed a straightforward transition-metal-free method which allows the efficient chemoselective C–H alkylation of pyrazine under mild reaction conditions (room temperature, 30 min) using the lithium homoalkylzincate [(PMDETA)LiZn*t*Bu₃] (PMDETA = *N,N,N',N'',N'''*-pentamethyldiethylenetriamine) (Scheme 1).⁹

Scheme 1. Zincate-Mediated Regioselective C–H Alkylation of Pyrazine

Structural characterization of the organometallic intermediate prior to the hydrolysis step, I (Scheme 1), showed that the addition of a *tert*-butyl group from the zincate anion had taken place at the C2 position of the heterocycle, bringing about its dearomatization. Significantly, neutral Zn*t*Bu₂ on its own fails to promote the addition of a *t*Bu group to pyrazine, demonstrating that formation of I is a genuine example of cooperative bimetallic synthesis.¹⁰ The greater nucleophilic power of the lithium zincate species in comparison to that of neutral organozinc reagents has also been assessed using theoretical calculations by Uchiyama et al. within the context of 1,2-addition reactions to formaldehyde.¹¹ Similarly, work carried out by Ishihara^{12a,b} and our group^{12c} has shown the successful chemoselective alkylation of ketones by magnesium trialkyl zincates generated in situ via salt metathesis of the relevant Grignard reagents and ZnCl₂.¹² The enhanced reactivities exhibited by these mixed-metal systems can be rationalized in terms of metal–metal cooperative effects.¹⁰ Thus, by forming a zincate anion it is possible to overcome the large kinetic barrier of the lower polarity Zn–C bonds in neutral ZnR₂ reagents, but the more electropositive metal present in these reagents (either Li or Mg) also plays a major role in these transformations, acting as an internal Lewis acid, by anchoring the organic substrate (thus lowering entropic barriers) and facilitating its nucleophilic attack by the {ZnR₃}[−] anion.

Building on these initial studies, herein we extend this bimetallic approach using lithium aryl zincate combinations to promote transition-metal-free, direct arylation of electron-deficient N-heterocycles, employing the biologically significant substrate acridine (*acr*) as a case study. By isolating key organometallic intermediates involved in these reactions prior to the hydrolysis/oxidation stages, new insights have been gained

into how these bimetallic arylating reagents operate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis and Characterization of Homoleptic Aryllithium Zincates. To avoid possible side reactions,¹³ for this study we employed the homoleptic aryl zincates [LiZnPh₃] (2) and [Li₂ZnPh₄] (3). Pioneered by Wittig in 1951, hetero-

bimetallic 2 is a classical reagent in mixed-metal chemistry, as the study of its reactivity for the deprotonation of fluorene constitutes one of the first reported synthetic applications of alkali–metal zincate reagents.¹⁴ In this epochal report, 2 is prepared in situ by reacting equimolar amounts of PhLi and ZnPh₂ in diethyl ether. Using a similar interlocking cocomplexation approach,¹⁵ we began our investigations by exploring the reactions of different stoichiometries of phenyllithium and ZnPh₂ (1).¹⁶ A 1:1 ratio of these monometallic aryl reagents in a THF/hexane solvent mixture furnished Wittig's lithium tris(aryl) zincate [LiZnPh₃] (2) as a microcrystalline solid in a 68% yield. Its higher order¹⁷ congener [Li₂ZnPh₄] (3) was isolated as a colorless oil using the same method but employing 2 mol equiv of PhLi (Scheme 2). It should be noted

Scheme 2. Interlocking Cocomplexation Reactions To Form Lithium Phenyl Zincates 2 and 3^{17,18}

that compounds 2 and 3 were obtained with three and four THF solvate molecules, respectively.¹⁸ Lithium zincates 2 and 3 were both characterized in *d*₈-THF solutions by multinuclear (¹H, ¹³C, and ⁷Li) NMR spectroscopy (Table 1). For the classical zincate 2, crystals of its dibutyl ether solvate [LiZnPh₃(OBu₂)₂] (2·2OBu₂) could be isolated by carrying out the cocomplexation reaction in neat hexane using a commercial solution of PhLi in dibutyl ether, and its solid-state structure was determined by X-ray crystallographic studies (Figure 2).

In the crystal 2·2OBu₂ forms a contact ion pair lithium zincate arrangement. Zinc is σ-bonded to three phenyl groups in a trigonal-planar geometry (sum of the angles around Zn 359.99°), whereas lithium π-engages with two of the three Ph rings, adopting an orthogonal disposition (dihedral angle between the plane defined by C13–C18 and C1–C6 phenyl rings and the plane defined by C13LiC1 77.9(1)°), and is further solvated by two molecules of di-*n*-butyl ether (Figure 2). It should be noted that a similar distinct σ/π bonding preference of Zn and the alkali metal in aryl zincate intermediates has been previously described in the literature within the context of alkali–metal zination (AMMzn) chemistry of aromatic substrates, where it seems to play an important role in tuning the overall regioselectivity of the metalation processes.¹⁹

This contact structure of 2·2OBu₂, with Li and Zn separated by 2.753(4) Å, is in contrast with that reported for the same zincate anion in [{Mg₂Br₃(THF)₆}⁺{ZnPh₃}[−]], which exhibits a solvent-separated ion pair structure.²⁰ Although the average Zn–C bond distances for each compound are similar (2.019 Å for 2·2OBu₂ vs 2.007 Å for the Mg zincate), a close inspection of the individual values shows that the Zn–C bond distance involving the Ph groups which interact with the Li atom in 2·OBu₂ are marginally elongated (2.034(3) and 2.032(3) Å) in comparison to that observed for the terminal Ph group (1.991(2) Å). Interestingly, reflecting its anionic constitution, these bridging Zn–C bond distances are noticeably shorter than those found in the homometallic precursor [ZnPh₂] (1), which displays a simple dimeric motif {ZnC₂}₂ (average Zn–

Table 1. Selected Chemical Shifts (ppm) in the ^1H , ^{13}C , and ^7Li NMR of PhLi, ZnPh₂, and Compounds 2 and 3 in Deuterated THF Solutions at 298 K¹⁸

	PhLi ($\delta(^7\text{Li})$ 3.4)		ZnPh ₂ (1)		LiZnPh ₃ (2) ($\delta(^7\text{Li})$ 0.2)		Li ₂ ZnPh ₄ (3) ($\delta(^7\text{Li})$ 1.7)	
	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C
ipso		187.5		156.8		168.3		173.1
<i>o</i> -Ph	7.98	144.2	7.55	126.1	7.88	141.1	7.93	142.8
<i>m</i> -Ph	6.93	125.0	7.09	127.2	7.05	126.1	7.01	125.8
<i>p</i> -Ph	6.83	123.3	7.02	139.6	6.96	124.2	6.90	123.9

Figure 2. Molecular structure of [LiZnPh₃(OBu₂)₂] (2·2OBu₂) with ellipsoids drawn at the 50% probability level and hydrogen atoms and minor disorder on the OBu₂ ligands omitted for clarity. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg): Zn1–C1 2.034(3), Zn1–C7 1.991(2), Zn1–C13 2.032(3), Li1–C1 2.494(5), Li1–C6 2.786(5), Li1–C13 2.521(5), Li1–C18 2.832(5); C7–Zn1–C13 122.22(10), C7–Zn1–C1 120.77(11), C13–Zn1–C1 117.00(10), O1–Li1–C1 113.9(2), O1–Li1–C13 98.1(2), O1–Li1–O2 112.8(3).

C_{bridge} distance 2.207 Å).²¹ Although there are only a handful of tris(aryl) alkali-metal zincates structurally characterized,²² in most cases their aryl groups carry heteroatomic substituents, such as NMe₂ and CON^tPr₂, which datively stabilize the alkali metal. In contrast, in 2·2OBu₂, two of the phenyl rings coordinate to the lithium atom via $\eta^2 \pi$ contacts involving their ipso and one of their ortho carbons, with Li–C distances

ranging from 2.494(5) to 2.832(5) Å. These values are considerably longer than those previously found in structures of PhLi solvates such as [(PhLi·OEt₂)₄] and [PhLi·(–)sparteine]₂, which exhibit Li–C_{ipso} σ bridges with average lengths of 2.335 and 2.299 Å, respectively.^{23,24}

Multinuclear (^1H , ^{13}C , and ^7Li) NMR spectroscopic studies of 2 confirmed its bimetallic constitution in deuterated THF solutions (Table 1). The ^1H NMR spectrum showed a single set of signals for the Ph groups (see the Supporting Information and Table 1) consistent with the formation of solvent-separated ion pair species in solution, where all the phenyl groups are equivalent. Its ^{13}C NMR spectrum displayed an informative resonance at 168.3 ppm for the ipso C of the Ph groups, at a chemical shift intermediate between those observed for the relevant ipso C's in the spectra of PhLi (187.5 ppm) and Ph₂Zn (156.8 ppm). Following a trend previously reported in NMR studies of alkali-metal zincates,²⁴ this value is closer to that exhibited by the zinc species than that of the lithium precursor, indicative of a significant proportion of “zinc character” being retained in the mixed-metal species 2. The presence of lithium was confirmed by a sharp singlet at 0.2 ppm in the ^7Li NMR spectrum. Interestingly, ^1H – ^7Li -HOESY experiments carried out on solutions of 3 in deuterated THF and C₆D₆ solutions suggested that the structure of this zincate in solution changes depending on the donor ability of the deuterated solvent. Thus, in *d*₈-THF solutions, no HOESY cross peaks were observed for the interaction of ^7Li with any of the aromatic protons of the phenyl groups, supporting the formation of solvent-separated ion-pair species. In contrast,

Table 2. Transition-Metal-Free C9 Arylation of acr using Zn Arylating Reagents 1–3 and PhLi

entry	MPh	<i>n</i>	time (h)	<i>T</i> (°C)	yield (%) ^a	
					4	5
1	ZnPh ₂ (1)	1.2	24	66	0	0
2	LiZnPh ₃ (2)	1.2	24	66	56	8
3	Li ₂ ZnPh ₄ (3)	1.2	24	66	68	10
4 ^b	ZnPh ₂ (1)	1.2	0.33	125	0	0
5 ^b	LiZnPh ₃ (2)	1.2	0.33	125	70	6
6 ^{b,c}	LiZnPh ₃ (2)	1.2	0.33	125	0	61
7 ^b	Li ₂ ZnPh ₄ (3)	1.2	0.33	125	95	0
8 ^{b,c}	Li ₂ ZnPh ₄ (3)	1.2	0.33	125	0	71
9 ^{b,c}	PhLi	1.2	0.33	125	0	49

^aA 0.5 mmol amount of acridine (acr) was employed. Yields were determined through addition of an internal standard (10 mol % ferrocene or hexamethylbenzene) after the hydrolysis step. ^bReaction was carried out under microwave irradiation. ^cA 1.5 equiv amount of DDQ was added to the hydrolyzed sample.

using C₆D₆ solutions, a strong interaction between ⁷Li and the *o*-H of the Ph groups was observed, which is consistent with a contact ion pair structure, similar to that found in the solid state for the dibutyl ether solvate 2·2OBu₂ (see the Supporting Information for details).

Although the higher-order zincate could only be isolated as a colorless oil and therefore its structure could not be determined crystallographically, it is pertinent that a few related lithium tetraorganozincates of general formula Li₂ZnR₄ (R = alkyl, aryl) have been structurally defined, forming contact ion pair aggregates, with two Li cations oppositely disposed to a central dianionic {ZnR₄}²⁻ tetrahedron within a trinuclear Li···Zn···Li chain arrangement.^{17b,22a,25} The same structural motif has been described previously by Weiss in a magnesium analogue of 3, the tetrakis(aryl)magnesiato [(TMEDA)₂Li₂MgPh₄].²⁶ Compound 3 was characterized by a combination of ¹H, ¹³C, and ⁷Li NMR spectroscopic studies (see the Supporting Information and Table 1). A singlet (1.7 ppm) in the ⁷Li NMR spectrum of 3 in deuterated THF solution established the presence of lithium. Its ¹H NMR spectrum revealed a single set of resonances for the Ph groups, at chemical shifts similar to those found for the tris(aryl) derivative 2.²⁷ Reflecting the dianionic character of 3, the ipso C of the Ph groups resonates at 173.1 ppm, which is noticeably deshielded from that observed for monoanionic 2 (169.3 ppm) and neutral ZnPh₂ (156.8 ppm).^{17a}

Reactivity Studies: Zincate-Mediated Arylation of Acridine. As mentioned above, previous studies have shown that ZnPh₂ (1) is unable to transfer one of its phenyl groups to acridine (acr) in the absence of a transition-metal catalyst and harsh reaction conditions (130 °C, 20 h).^{5c} We initially examined the reaction of acr with zincates 2 and 3 at room temperature in THF,²⁸ however, after 48 h, no arylation products were observed. When the temperature was increased to 66 °C over a 24 h period, it was possible to detect the formation in both cases of the dihydroacridine 4 as the major reaction product (in yields of 56% for 2 and 68% for 3; Table 2, entries 2 and 3), resulting from the successful arylation of acr, along with small amounts of the fully aromatized product 9-phenylacridine (5) (8 and 10% yields, respectively; entries 2 and 3, Table 2). Since extended reaction times were required to promote the aryl transfer processes, alternative conditions utilizing microwave irradiation were investigated (125 °C, 20 min; entries 4–8, Table 2), as previous studies in organozincate chemistry have shown that the use of microwave irradiation can boost the reactivity of these bimetallic systems.²⁹ Furthermore, biaryl coupling of electron-deficient N-heterocyclic molecules such as pyrazine and haloarenes has been accomplished by using KO^{*t*}Bu under microwave irradiation.³⁰ Control reactions show that even under these conditions ZnPh₂ itself is unable to perform the nucleophilic addition, (entry 4, Table 2). However, ¹H NMR analysis of the crude reaction mixtures containing acr and 1.2 equiv of the zincate 2 showed almost complete consumption of the starting materials with the subsequent formation of the arylation products 4 and 5 (yields of 70 and 6%, respectively; entry 5, Table 2). Under these reaction conditions, tetraorganozincate 3 furnished 4 in almost quantitative yield (95%; entry 7). The reaction of acr with substoichiometric amounts of higher-order zincate 3 (0.6 equiv) was also investigated in order to assess if 3 could transfer more than one of its Ph groups. However, under these conditions 5 was obtained in a modest 56% yield (see the Supporting Information for details). The enhanced nucleophil-

icity of bimetallic reagents 2 and 3 in comparison to parent ZnPh₂ can be attributed to a combination of the anionic activation of the zinc reagent, by forming {ZnPh₃}⁻ or {ZnPh₄}²⁻ species, and the Lewis acid activation of the N-heterocyclic substrate acr by its dative coordination to the Li centers. A comparison of the yields obtained for the dihydroacridine product 4 showed a superior arylation power for zincate 3 in comparison to 2 (95% vs 70%), a pattern following the degree of negative charge in the zinc local coordination (i.e., 2 vs 1 vs 0 within 3, 2, and 1, respectively). The enhanced nucleophilicity of higher-order zincates over their triorgano analogues has been previously noted by Kondo and Uchiyama in several organic transformations, including Michael addition, carbozincation, and epoxide ring-opening reactions.^{17a,31} Since in both cases even under aerobic conditions the oxidation of dihydroacridine 4 to give 5 does not go to completion, 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (DDQ)^{1g,5a} was employed as an external oxidant, affording the aromatized product 5 in 71% yield when using zincate 3, whereas its lower-order congener furnished 5 in a 61% yield (entries 8 and 6, respectively, Table 2).³² Interestingly, illustrating the cooperative effect of Li and Zn in these bimetallic reagents, when acr was reacted with polar PhLi under the same reaction conditions, 5 was obtained in a diminished 49% yield (entry 9, Table 2).

In order to isolate and characterize the organometallic species along the reaction coordinate to 4 and 5 prior to the hydrolysis step, the reaction of equimolar equivalents of acr with 2 was carried out at 125 °C using microwave irradiation for 20 min. This afforded a dark brown solution which, after storage at -70 °C, deposited light brown crystals of [(THF)₃Li(NC₁₃H₉-Ph)] (6) in a 31% yield (see Scheme 3 and the Supporting Information).

Scheme 3. Synthesis of the Organometallic Intermediates 6–8 Resulting from the Reactions of acr with (a) LiZnPh₃ in THF under Microwave Irradiation, (b) PhLi in THF at 0 °C, and (c) ZnPh₂ in Hexane at Room Temperature, Respectively

X-ray crystallographic studies revealed the monometallic composition of 6 (Figure 3), confirming the successful addition of 3 across one C=C bond of acr, selectively introducing a Ph group to the C9 position (i.e., C18), giving rise to a new fused tricyclic amide fragment which binds to Li. As expected, the Li–N bond distance (1.989(4) Å) is shorter than those reported in the literature where related N-heterocyclic molecules such as pyridine and quinoline act as neutral two-electron donors to Li atoms³³ but is similar to that recently found in the 1,2-dihydropyridyllithium complex [2-*t*BuC₅H₅N]Li(Me₆TREN)] (Me₆TREN = tris(*N,N*-dimethyl-2-aminoethyl)amine), resulting from the addition of *t*BuLi to

Figure 3. Molecular structure of $[(\text{THF})_3\text{Li}(\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{-Ph})]$ (6) with ellipsoids drawn at the 50% probability level and hydrogen atoms (excluding H18) omitted for clarity. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg): Li1–N1 1.989(4), Li1–O1 1.974(4), Li1–O2 1.930(4), Li1–O3 2.014(4); O1–Li1–O2 104.72(16), O1–Li1–O3 98.14(16), O1–Li1–N1 109.36(16), O2–Li1–O3 105.19(15), O2–Li1–N1 120.64(19), N1–Li1–O3 115.96(17), C24–N1–C26 115.47(15), C24–N1–Li1 118.42(16), C26–N1–Li1 125.65(16).

pyridine (1.971(2) Å).³⁴ Lithium completes its distorted-tetrahedral geometry (angles ranging from 105.19(15) to 125.65(16)°) in 6 by coordinating to three solvate molecules of THF. Demonstrating its loss of aromaticity, the new heterocyclic ring is noticeably puckered, with C18 representing now a chiral sp^3 tetrahedral carbon which lies 0.316(3) Å outside the mean plane of the four sp^2 -hybridized carbons (C17, C19, C24, and C26). Furthermore, the bonding on the formerly aromatic central ring shows a clearly more localized double/single bond pattern (C–C distances ranging from 1.516(3) to 1.416(2) Å) in comparison with those previously involving the C atoms of the outer rings (C–C distances ranging from 1.415(2) to 1.369(3) Å).

Interestingly, a search of the Cambridge Structural Database found no precedents for an alkylated/arylated acridine structure of zinc or lithium, or indeed of any metal,³⁵ comparable to 6. Surprisingly, the “lithium-only” constitution of 6 contrasts with the heterobimetallic constitution of the aryating reagent 2, although paradoxically it represents, to the best of our knowledge, the first example of a structurally defined reaction intermediate of the nucleophilic arylation of a zincate to an N-heterocyclic molecule. These findings contrast somewhat with the bimetallic structure reported for the alkylation product I resulting from the reaction of pyrazine by $[\text{LiZnBu}_3(\text{PMEDTA})]$ (Scheme 1),⁹ although this could perhaps be attributed to the presence of two N atoms in the heterocycle, where each of them coordinates to a different metal, allowing the trapping of the neutral $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{Bu}_2$ fragment.

Fitting its structure in the solid state, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR studies of d_8 -THF solutions of 5 confirmed the dearomatization of the acridine central ring. Thus, an informative singlet at 5.03 ppm is observed in the ^1H NMR spectrum, which can be assigned to the H originally attached to the C9 atom of *acr* and, as could be expected, appears significantly upfield in comparison to that observed for *acr* (at 8.88 ppm). Reflecting its change in hybridization, C9 in 6 resonates at 50.8 ppm in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum, whereas in free *acr* it appears at 136.3 ppm (see the Supporting Information for experimental details). In order to gain a better understanding of the fate of zinc and how these mixed-metal reagents operate in the arylation process, NMR analysis of the reaction crude of *acr* and 2 was carried out in d_8 -THF solvent. Despite the complexity of this

^1H NMR spectrum in the aromatic region (Figure S5 in the Supporting Information), a diagnostic singlet at 5.34 ppm was observed, which would suggest the presence of an anionic 9-phenyl-9-hydroacridine group similar to that present in 6 (δ $\text{CH}(\text{Ph})$ appears at 5.03 ppm; vide supra). A comparison of the aromatic region of the ^1H NMR spectrum of this crude reaction mixture with those obtained for zincate 2, ZnPh_2 (1), and the lithium addition product 6 (Figure S7 in the Supporting Information) suggests that these three species are present in the reaction mixture, although the chemical shifts observed for the resonances attributed to ZnPh_2 and 6 appear at slightly different (but noticeable) chemical shifts. A plausible explanation would be that, in solution, these two species are interacting with each other, forming the heteroleptic zincate $[\text{LiZn}(\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{-Ph})\text{Ph}_2]$ which, under the conditions required for crystallization, can then undergo redistribution to give a mixture of homometallic 6 and ZnPh_2 .³⁶

Considering the single-metal composition of 6, we also examined the reaction of *acr* with PhLi . Ray et al.^{5a} have reported the formation of 9-phenylacridine (5) by treating *acr* with 3 equiv of PhLi/TMEDA (N,N,N',N' -tetramethylethylenediamine) in THF at 0 °C, followed by a hydrolysis/oxidation step. Interestingly, when we carried out this reaction under these conditions, we observed first the formation of a dark brown solution which over time developed a persistent intense violet color, strongly suggesting the formation of a radical species. Storage of this solution at room temperature allowed the isolation of the mixed donor complex $[(\text{THF})(\text{TMEDA})\text{Li}\{\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{-Ph}^{\cdot-}\}]$ (7) as dark purple crystals in 42% yield. X-ray crystallographic studies established the molecular structure of 7 as a novel radical anion lithium complex, comprising one Li atom, solvated by a chelating TMEDA ligand and molecule of THF, which is bonded to the N atom of the radical anion $\{\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{-Ph}^{\cdot-}\}$, resulting from the replacement of the H atom attached at the C9 position of the original *acr* ring (i.e., C7) by a Ph group (Figure 4).³⁷

The monomeric arrangement of 7 is somewhat reminiscent to that described for 6, although in the latter the anionic N-heterocyclic ring is no longer aromatic (vide supra). Reflecting the radical anionic constitution of the $\{\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{-Ph}^{\cdot-}\}$

Figure 4. Molecular structure of $[(\text{THF})(\text{TMEDA})\text{Li}\{\text{NC}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{-Ph}^{\cdot-}\}]$ (7) with ellipsoids drawn at the 30% probability level. Hydrogen atoms disordered within THF/TMEDA³⁸ are omitted for clarity. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg): N1–Li1 2.070(6), N1–C13 1.367(3), N1–C1 1.370(4), C7–C8 1.425(4), C7–C14 1.489(4), C7–C6 1.422(4), C1–C6 1.440(4), C13–C8 1.444(4); Li1–N1–C1 118.7(2), Li1–N1–C13 122.1(2), C1–N1–C13 117.8(2), C6–C7–C8 118.5(3), C6–C7–C14 120.6(3), C8–C7–C14 120.8(2).

fragment, the Li1–N1 distance in **7** (2.070(6) Å) is elongated by 0.081 Å from that observed in **6**. Furthermore, the carbon atom now carrying the phenyl substituent, C7, exhibits sp² hybridization (sum of angles around C7 359.9°), lying nearly coplanar with the mean plane defined by C1, C6, C8, and C13 (located just 0.023(3) Å outside of this plane). Consistent with a high degree of electronic delocalization within this heterocyclic system,³⁸ a close inspection of the C–C bond distances within the fused tricyclic aromatic unit shows that they cover the narrow range from 1.369(4) to 1.440(4) Å, with the incoming Ph group adopting a staggered orthogonal disposition (dihedral angle between the Ph and the acridine rings, 63.38(8)°). As far as we can ascertain, **7** represents the first structural elucidation of a radical anion derived from 9-phenylacridine. Interestingly, in an earlier report,³⁹ Bard et al. assessed the geometry of this radical anion with the aid of EPR and theoretical studies, estimating the twist angle between the Ph and the acridine ring to be 65°, which is in close agreement with that determined for **7**.⁴⁰

Demonstrating its paramagnetic nature, solid-state EPR measurements of a powdered sample of **7** at various temperatures (4, 20, and 70 K) showed a strong resonance centered at a *g* value of 2.0056 arising from the unpaired electron of the radical anion (Figure 5 and the Supporting

Figure 5. Variable-temperature (4 to 70 K) X-band (9.421 GHz) EPR spectra of a solid sample of **7**.

Information). The lack of resolution caused by *g* and *A* strains and the expected short spin–spin relaxation times preclude the observation of hyperfine splittings. The obtained *g* value is similar to those reported for other organic radical anions, as for example in the alkali-metal salts of a 2,2'-bipyridyl radical anion such as [K(2,2'-bipy)(en)] (en = ethylenediamine; *g* = 2.0033 in the solid state).⁴¹

The different nature of the anionic ligands present in the intermediates **6** and **7** indicates that different reaction pathways must be in operation for the arylation of *acr*, depending on the organometallic reagent and the conditions employed. Thus, while the zincate-mediated process appears to formally be a polar addition reaction, though radicals may well be involved, when 3 equiv of PhLi/TMEDA is employed, a radical (single-electron transfer) mechanism appears to be definitively operative.⁴² In this regard, it should be noted that related studies on the addition of PhLi to C=O bonds of ketones and aldehydes have established that these reactions can take place via an electron-transfer/radical-coupling sequence.⁴³ These findings not only highlight the complexity of these arylation processes but also draw attention to the significance of identifying the organometallic intermediates involved, which

otherwise, if these reactions were carried out in situ, followed by subsequent hydrolysis and oxidation states would have remained hidden, affording in both cases the same organic product, 9-phenylacridine (**5**).⁴⁴

For comparison, we also carried out the reaction of ZnPh₂ (**1**) with *acr* in hexane, which furnished the coordination adduct [(*acr*)ZnPh₂] (**8**) in a 29% crystalline yield. ¹H and ¹³C NMR analysis of the filtrate solution showed that **8** is the only species present in solution, suggesting that its modest isolated crystalline yield is due to its solubility in hexane under the crystallization conditions. The molecular structure of **8** was established by X-ray crystallography (Figure 6). In contrast with

Figure 6. Molecular structure of [(*acr*)ZnPh₂] (**8**) with ellipsoids drawn at the 50% probability level and hydrogen atoms omitted for clarity. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg): Zn1–C1 1.942(11), Zn1–C7 1.9647(13), Zn1–N1 2.1598(11); C7–Zn1–N1 146.9(5), C7–Zn1–N1 108.97(5), C1–Zn1–N1 104.1(5).

the dimeric structure of **1** (vide supra),²¹ **8** displays a monomeric arrangement, where the trigonal-planar Zn atom coordinates to two terminal Ph groups and the N of the neutral *acr* ligand. The Zn–N distance at 2.1598(11) Å is comparable to that previously reported for the related pyridine adduct [Ph₂Zn(NC₅H₅)₂] (average 2.1505 Å).⁴⁵ Multinuclear (¹H and ¹³C) NMR spectroscopic analysis of **8** in C₆D₆ shows that its structural integrity is retained in solution.⁴⁶ Thus, the relevant resonances of *acr* in **8** in both NMR spectra appear at distinctive downfield shifts in comparison to those observed for free *acr* (for example, in the ¹H NMR spectrum, C₉-H in **8** resonates at 8.10 ppm vs 7.97 ppm for *acr*). It is noteworthy that coordination adducts similar to **8**, where the relevant bis(aryl)zinc reagent is coordinated to the N-heterocyclic substrate, have been proposed to be involved in the first stages of the transition-metal-catalyzed processes, providing the activation of the organic molecule toward nucleophilic Ni- or Rh-mediated arylation.^{1g}

CONCLUSIONS

This study has examined the potential applications of lithium homo(aryl) zincates for chemoselective C–H arylation reactions of electron-deficient N-heterocyclic molecules, using acridine as a case study. The aryating reagents LiZnPh₃ (**2**) and Li₂ZnPh₄ (**3**) have been prepared straightforwardly using cocomplexation by mixing appropriate amounts of PhLi with ZnPh₂ (**1**). X-ray crystallographic studies established the molecular structure of the dibutyl ether solvate of **2**, [LiZnPh₃(OBu₂)₂] (2·2OBu₂). Significantly, though the parent

triorganozincate 2 was first introduced by Wittig over 60 years ago, its structure still remains elusive.

Using microwave irradiation, both zincates can regioselectively transfer a Ph group to the C9 position of *acr*, affording mixtures of the arylation products 9,10-dihydro-9-phenylacridine (4) and 9-phenylacridine (5), without the need for transition-metal catalysis. Reflecting its higher degree of activation, the higher-order zincate 3 showed an enhanced arylation power, furnishing the reduced product 4 in a 95% yield (vs 70% using lower-order 2), which can be oxidized to 5 with DDQ. Under these conditions, structural evidence for the success of the reaction has been gained by isolating the addition product [(THF)₃Li(NC₁₃H₉Ph)] (6). Interestingly, attempts to prepare 6 using PhLi/TMEDA (3 equiv) and *acr* led to the formation of a different type of arylation product, affording crystals of novel paramagnetic [(THF)(TMEDA)Li{NC₁₃H₈-Ph[•]}] (7), where now Li is bonded to a radical anion of 9-phenylacridine. Collectively these structural studies indicate that different reaction pathways must be in operation for the arylation of *acr*, depending on the organometallic reagent and the reaction conditions employed. Thus, while the zincate-mediated process appears to be a polar addition reaction, at least formally, using an excess of PhLi, the arylation process occurs, at least in part, via a radical mechanism.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General Conditions. All reactions were performed under a protective argon atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. Hexane, tetrahydrofuran (THF), and toluene were dried by heating to reflux over sodium benzophenone and distilled under nitrogen prior to use. PhLi (1.8 M solution in dibutyl ether) and acridine were purchased from Aldrich Chemicals and used as received.¹⁶ Ph₂Zn was prepared according to a literature method. Solvent-free PhLi was prepared as a solid and stored in the glovebox, following the reported procedure.¹⁶ NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DPX 400 MHz spectrometer, operating at 400.13 MHz for ¹H, 150.32 MHz for ⁷Li, and 100.62 MHz for ¹³C. Elemental analyses were carried out on a PerkinElmer 2400 elemental analyzer. X-Band (9.42 GHz) EPR spectra were determined with powdered samples on a Bruker ESP300E spectrometer, with a liquid helium cryostat. Satisfactory elemental analyses of the air-sensitive products 2·2OBu₂ (too air sensitive) and 7 (cocrystalline mixture of two donor variants)⁴⁸ could not be obtained.

Crystallographic Data. All crystallographic measurements were made with Oxford Diffraction Instruments. Structures were refined against *F*² and against all independent reflections to convergence using SHELXL.⁴⁷ Structure 6 contains disordered THF solvent of crystallization that could not be satisfactorily modeled. Thus, this structure was refined against a reflection data set which was output by the SQUEEZE routine implemented in PLATON.⁴⁸ Structure 7 is a cocrystal of [Li(phenylacridine)(THF)₃] and [Li(phenylacridine)-(THF)(TMEDA)], with both species occupying the same crystallographic sites. Site occupancy factors were refined to 0.735(3):0.265(3) in favor of the first-named species. Bond lengths of the resulting disordered fragments were restrained, and both restraints and constraints were required to be applied to the displacement parameters of the same groups. Similar treatments were used for the disordered ether ligands of 2·2*On*Bu₂ and the disordered phenyl ring of 8. Selected crystallographic details are presented in Table S1 in the Supporting Information, and full information in CIF format has been deposited with the CCDC (1035850–1035853).

Synthesis of LiZnPh₃ (2). To a solution of ZnPh₂ (0.11 g, 0.5 mmol) in THF (2 mL) was added PhLi (0.04 g, 0.5 mmol), affording a pale yellow solution that was stirred at room temperature for 10 min. Hexane was then introduced (5 mL). Refrigeration of this solution at -68 °C afforded a crop of microcrystalline solid (yield 0.18 g, 68%). NMR analysis of this solid in C₆D₆ showed the presence of three

solvating molecules of THF. This has been taken into account when calculating the yield of 2 and its elemental analysis. Anal. Calcd for C₃₀H₃₉LiO₃Zn: C, 69.30; H, 7.56. Found: C, 70.05; H, 7.31. ¹H NMR (400.13 MHz, 298 K *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 7.88 (d, 6H, H_{ortho}), 7.05 (t, 6H, H_{meta}), 6.96 (t, 3H, H_{para}), 3.58 (m, 12H, H _{α} -THF), 1.74 (m, 12H, H _{β} -THF). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (100.62 MHz, 298 K, *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 169.3 (C_{ipso}), 141.3 (C_{ortho}), 125.9 (C_{meta}), 124.0 (C_{para}), 68.4 (C _{α} -THF), 26.2 (C _{β} -THF). ⁷Li NMR (298 K, *d*₈-THF, reference LiCl in D₂O at 0.00 ppm; δ (ppm)): 0.2.

Synthesis of [LiZnPh₃(OBu)₂] (2·2OBu₂). To a suspension of ZnPh₂ (0.11 g, 0.5 mmol) in hexane (5 mL) was added PhLi (0.28 mL of a 1.8 M solution in dibutyl ether, 0.5 mmol). Toluene (15 mL) was then introduced and the resulting suspension was gently heated with a heat gun, affording a pale yellow solution from which colorless crystals of 2·2OBu₂ were deposited upon cooling this solution to -28 °C (yield 0.14 g, 57%). ¹H NMR (400.13 MHz, 298 K *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 7.90 (d, 6H, H_{ortho}), 7.05 (t, 6H, H_{meta}), 6.90 (t, 3H, H_{para}), 3.41 (m, 8H, OCH₂, OBu₂), 1.55 (m, 8H, CH₂, OBu₂), 1.44 (m, 8H, CH₂, OBu₂), 0.099 (m, 12H, CH₃, OBu₂). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (100.62 MHz, 298 K, *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 169.4 (C_{ipso}), 141.1 (C_{ortho}), 125.8 (C_{meta}), 123.8 (C_{para}), 70.9 (OCH₂, OBu₂), 32.6 (CH₂, OBu₂), 20.1 (CH₂, OBu₂), 14.1 (CH₃, OBu₂). ⁷Li NMR (298 K, *d*₈-THF, reference LiCl in D₂O at 0.00 ppm; δ (ppm)): 1.1.

Synthesis of Li₂ZnPh₄ (3). To a solution of Ph₂Zn (0.11 g, 0.5 mmol) in THF (0.5 mL) was added PhLi (0.08 g, 1 mmol). The resulting pale yellow solution was stirred at room temperature for 10 min. Volatiles were removed under vacuum, and the resulting colorless oil was dissolved in neat hexane (2 mL), affording a pale yellow solution. Despite several attempts, with this solution stored at different temperatures (3, -28, and -68 °C), no crystalline solid could be obtained. Removal of all volatiles under vacuum led to the isolation of 3 as a colorless oil. ¹H NMR analysis of this oil in deuterated THF showed the presence of four solvating molecules of THF. ¹H NMR (400.13 MHz, 298 K *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 7.93 (d, 8H, H_{ortho}), 7.01 (t, 8H, H_{meta}), 6.96 (t, 4H, H_{para}), 3.56 (m, 16H, H _{α} -THF), 1.74 (m, 16H, H _{β} -THF). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (100.62 MHz, 298 K, *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 173.1 (broad, C_{ipso}), 142.8 (C_{ortho}), 125.8 (C_{meta}), 123.9 (C_{para}), 68.3 (C _{α} -THF), 26.3 (C _{β} -THF). ⁷Li NMR (298 K, *d*₈-THF, reference LiCl in D₂O at 0.00 ppm; δ (ppm)): 1.7.

Synthesis of [(THF)₃Li(NC₁₃H₉Ph)] (6). Acridine (0.5 mL of a 1 M solution in THF, 0.5 mmol) was added to a THF solution (2 mL) of zincate 2 (0.5 mmol) prepared *in situ* as above. This mixture was then microwaved (125 °C) for 20 min, affording a dark brown solution. The solution was filtered and stored at -70 °C overnight, resulting in the formation of pale brown crystals of 6 (0.24 g, 31% yield). Anal. Calcd for C₃₁H₄₀LiNO₃: C, 77.31; H, 8.37; N, 2.91. Found: C, 77.46; H, 8.06; N, 3.11. ¹H NMR (400.13 MHz, 298 K *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 7.11 (d, 2 H, H_{ortho}, Ph), 7.07 (t, 2 H, H_{meta}, Ph), 6.97 (t, 1H, H_{para}, Ph), 6.76 (d, 2H, NC₁₃C₉), 6.69 (t, 2H, NC₁₃C₉), 6.49 (d, 2H, NC₁₃C₉), 6.23 (t, 2H, NC₁₃C₉), 5.03 (s, 1H, CHPh, NC₁₃C₉), 3.61 (m, 12 H, H _{α} -THF), 1.76 (m, 12H, H _{β} -THF). ¹³C {¹H} NMR (100.62 MHz, 298 K, *d*₈-THF; δ (ppm)): 153.9, 151.7 (C_{quaternary}, NC₁₃C₉), 141.2 (C_{ipso}, Ph), 129.3 (C1, NC₁₃C₉), 128.3 (C_{ortho}, Ph), 128.0 (C_{meta}, Ph), 126.3 (C3, NC₁₃C₉), 125.3 (C_{para}, Ph), 118.8 (C4, NC₁₃C₉), 114.1 (C2, NC₁₃C₉), 68.2 (C _{α} -THF), 50.8 (CHPh, NC₁₃C₉), 26.3 (C _{β} -THF). ⁷Li NMR (298 K, *d*₈-THF, reference LiCl in D₂O at 0.00 ppm; δ (ppm)): 0.74 ppm.

Synthesis of [(THF)(TMEDA)Li{NC₁₃H₈-Ph[•]}] (7). To a solution of *acr* (0.18 g, 1 mmol) in THF (5 mL) was added TMEDA (0.45 mL, 3 mmol). The solution was cooled to 0 °C, PhLi (1.12 mL of a 0.8 M solution in dibutyl ether, 3 mmol) was added dropwise, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h before being slowly warmed to room temperature. The solution deposited a deep purple microcrystalline solid in a 42% yield (0.19 g) on standing at room temperature for over 3 days. The X-band (9.42 GHz) EPR spectra of a solid sample of 7 recorded at 4, 20, and 70 K revealed a strong resonance with a *g* value of 2.006.

Synthesis of [(*acr*)ZnPh₂] (8). To a suspension of Ph₂Zn (0.22 g, 1 mmol) in hexane (10 mL) was added acridine (0.18 g, 1 mmol). A 30 mL portion of hot toluene was added, giving a yellow solution

which was slowly cooled to room temperature using a hot water bath, resulting in the deposition of colorless crystals of **8** in a 29% yield (0.12 g). Anal. Calcd for C₂₅H₁₉NZn: C, 75.29; H, 4.80; N, 3.51 Found: C, 75.24; H, 4.79; N, 4.03. ¹H NMR (400.13 MHz, 298 K, C₆D₆; δ (ppm)): 8.26 (m, 2H, H₁-acr), 7.97 (s, 1 H, H₉-acr), 7.82–7.86 (m, 4H, H_{ortho}), 7.37 (m, 2H, H_{para}), 7.32–7.26 (m, 6 H, H_{meta} and H₄-acr overlapping), 7.03 (m, 2H, H₂-acr), 6.90–6.96 (m, 2 H, H₃-acr). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101.69 MHz, 298 K, C₆D₆; δ (ppm)): 154.9 (C_{ipso}, Ph), 147.7 (C_{quaternary}), 139.6 (C₉, acr), 139.5 (C_{ortho}, Ph), 132.7 (C₂, acr), 128.8 (C_{para}, Ph), 127.7 (C_{meta}, Ph), 127.4 (C₄, acr), 126.7 (C_{quaternary}, acr), 126.2 (C₃, acr), 125.9 (C₁, acr).

General Procedure for the Arylation Studies of acr. A THF solution (2 mL) of zincate **2** or **3** (0.5 mmol) prepared *in situ*, via cocomplexation of PhLi and ZnPh₂, was added to acridine (0.09 g, 0.5 mmol). This mixture was then microwaved (125 °C) for 20 min or refluxed over 14 h at 66 °C, before being quenched with a saturated aqueous brine solution (5 mL). The product was extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 5 mL), and the combined organic phases were dried (MgSO₄), filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure. Yields were determined by integration of the product resonances using ferrocene (10%) as internal standard in the ¹H NMR spectrum. The results of these studies are shown in Table 2. The reactions with ZnPh₂ (entries 1 and 4 of Table 2) were carried out under conditions identical with those described above, using a solution of 0.5 mol (0.11 g) of ZnPh₂. Examples of the ¹H NMR spectra obtained from these studies are shown in Figures S1 and S2 in the Supporting Information.

* Supporting Information

Text, figures, and CIF files giving additional experimental details, crystallographic results, and spectroscopic details. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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DEDICATION

In memory of Mike Lappert, whose vision and discoveries have greatly helped shape modern organometallic chemistry.

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- (37) The crystal structure of 7 is a cocrystalline mixture of the donor variants [(THF)₃Li{NC₁₃H₈-Ph⁻}] and [(THF)(TMEDA) Li{NC₁₃H₈-Ph⁻}]₂. Both molecules are disordered such that the [Li{NC₁₃H₈-Ph⁻}] fragments of each lie on the same crystallographic sites and appear well ordered, with the THF and TMEDA groups appearing disordered. Refinement of site occupancy factors gives a 0.735(3):0.265(3) ratio in favor of the [(THF)₃Li{NC₁₃H₈-Ph⁻}] species.
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